

A Model of Sustainable Reverse Logistics Strategies and Reduction in Greenhouse Gases

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Abstract

Sustainable development requires the firms to mitigate their use of extraneous resources and develop eco-friendly and green supply chain practices. Reverse logistics as a dynamic process of value-centric product flow-back to the supplier can practically aid to decrease the current global warming and greenhouse gases rate. This research aims to explore the tactics and strategies of sustainable indicators for a better global environment. This study is a systematic review. In the current examination, data were collected by exploring theoretical frameworks and ideas. This research concludes that the commitment of the industries to eco-friendly policies in supply chain management and a green system of reverse logistics can help mitigate global warming and the rate of greenhouse gases emission. Besides, reverse logistics process flow have a prominent role in the sustainability of industries by making effort to get the products back, from their final destinations to the suppliers, after use, for remanufacturing, recycling, or proper eco-friendly disposal. The final findings and effective indicators of the research have been demonstrated in the conceptual model of the paper.

Keywords: Reverse logistic, Sustainability, Greenhouse gases

Introduction

Nowadays, sustainable and green strategies are the mainstream of global concerns. There has been an increasing awareness in the issue of the world's environmental problems including air pollution, climate-changing, global warming, decrease in non-renewable resources, and especially greenhouse gas emissions. Meanwhile, in response to the mentioned environmental problems in the world, organizations need to apply green indicators to gain competitive advantages preserving sustainable and eco-friendly approaches in the process of their service and productions (Alizadeh Foroutan et al., 2020; Bhattacharyya and Sana, 2019). Consideration of carbon-decreasing policies while optimizing supply chain operations has become vital as governments and regulatory bodies throughout the world have implemented different carbon policies to reduce emissions of greenhouse gasses, especially carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (Acimovic et al., 2020; Cinar, 2021; Dev et al., 2020). Besides, greenhouse gases emissions from logistics and the relevant industries are rising at a greater concern than any other industry and the trend is expected to continue such that by 2030 these levels will be 80% higher than present levels unless there is a change (Daniel et al., 2020; Park et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, existing surveys indicate that the reverse logistics RL can be considered the most important and complex activity within a sustainable and green supply chain. Green essentials such as waste management, greenhouse gas emissions related to transportation modes, and production methods are embedded in the content of practical sustainable strategies. Incorporating RL in green supply chain management (GSCM) strategy is not a trivial task (Mishra et al., 2012). Furthermore, green supply chain management has been featured as a set of environmental management principles which could be utilized to taken into account environmental considerations in the forward and reverse logistics process (Cinar, 2021).

A successful manufacturing strategy must incorporate many different factors, both internally and externally to a firm. Nowadays, RL is considered as one of strategic plans for industrial organizations. Efficient RL, as an important component of GSCM, can provide a competitive advantage and customer-oriented social image and sustainable brand (Entezaminia et al., 2016). Namely, the reverse logistics process makes effort to get the products back, from their final destinations to the suppliers, after use, for remanufacturing, recycling, remanufacturing, or proper eco-friendly disposal.

The firms are adopting practices and processes in the supply chains that pose a lesser threat to the environment. Generally, reverse logistics is controlled by several factors such as environmental legislation; the extension of the responsibility of the manufacturer (Extended Producer Responsibility); the economy; and improved customer service. So basically the reverse logistics strategy can become a competitive force for the company (Usman and Nanda, 2017; Park et al., 2020). On the other hand, green logistics and reverse logistics (RL) as a particular form of logistics are increasingly considered by governments, industry owners and scholars nowadays, since it can lead to sustainable development, maintaining environmental standards and the stability of supply and distribution strategies. Collecting returned goods in the form of after-sales services can be mentioned as one of the most known types of RL.

Arguing the former or the latter reasons, in manufacturing management paradigm, implications of three R (Resource, reservation, reused for recycling) are more relevant to save our natural non-renewed resources as well as protect our environment from a large scale of pollution (Bhattacharyya and Sana, 2019). Reverse logistics is the ability of logistics management and activities that include the activities of reducing, regulating, and disposing of harmful or non-hazardous parts.

Since collecting returned goods (such as defective, damaged, expired, etc.) makes it possible to recycle and send them back into consumption cycle or destroy them with the least environmental pollutions, it is an effective way of contributing to environmental protection and at the same time obtaining economic benefits. Therefore, collecting returned goods is continuously becoming more common among various industries and also environmentally friendly organizations undertake parts of costs for both scientific researches and practical activities in this regard (Alizadeh Foroutan et al., 2020).

In a world with limited resources and limited disposal facilities, recovery, or improvements made to the product or material is key to supporting the population with rising consumption levels (Dev et al., 2020; Mishra et al., 2020).

In spite of all the existing alerts for moving towards ecologically sustainable system engineering and more resilient supply chains, it still remains difficult to make such changes in practice. In order to tackle this problem, more investigations should be made to fully understand the barriers, relationships and motivations lying behind creating the environmentally sustainable and resilient supply chains and RL (Sultan and Gaetani, 2016). Meanwhile, it is necessary to minimize costs and optimize the efficiency of natural resources, at the same time (Federico et al., 2020; Gu et al., 2019; Kusakci et al., 2019). Accordingly, many firms aim to reduce cost and they need to strike a balance between economic, social and ecological factors for sustainability. Several empirical studies have been carried out to investigate this relationship (Daniel et al., 2020). The main objective of this research and its proposed model is to formulate a profit function for reverse logistic level and the prominent variable dependent demand implementing green technology in the manufacturing industry for reduction of greenhouse gas emission. Moreover, coupled with the green concept, not only will increase the value of sustainability, but also will reduce the emissions of the greenhouse gases. In the same vein, the final research model of the current study offers the consequent indicators of the subject scope, based on the systematic review of investigated researches and excavated models.

Literature Review

The reverse logistics is considered as a part of supply chain management, but as an area, it has often been neglected and ignored in terms of analysis and priority (Marsillac, 2008). Historically, the process of the reverse logistics is relatively familiar in some industries (metal scrap, glass bottle and waste paper recycling), but its use was historically driven by the cost economics of product recycling over disposing (Fleischmann et al., 2000; Marsillac, 2008). In the last two decades, researchers have spent considerable effort studying how a reverse logistic can reduce cost, and how to establish an effective and efficient reverse logistics structure for different industries, such as automotive, electronics and recycling and reuse; using less resource material and environmentally hazardous material for products. Furthermore, reverse logistics can be implemented in different forms from collection to return shipments, followed by disassembly and reuse of collected parts. On the other hand, used products could be shredded and reentered into production as raw materials (Mutingi, 2014). Theoretically, RL is a process of planning, implementing, and controlling the efficiency and effectiveness of the flow of goods (raw materials, in-process inventories, or finished goods) and related information, from the consumer point back to the origin (Rogers and Tibben-Lembke, 1999). In this case, the handling of returned goods either salvage and scrap disposal, is part of a process that is closely related to reverse logistics, and is also a component of logistics that need more attention. Reverse logistics also involves the removal and disposal of waste material from the production, distribution and packaging.

Hazen and associates (2011) carried out a research in order to test the existence of influence between the reverse logistics flows, on one hand, and the green supply chain competitiveness. In a parallel survey, Fattahi and Govindan (2017) designed an integrated forward and reverse logistics network for the stochastic demand of new as well as used products and formulated stochastic and mixed-integer linear programming model. Also, they proposed a novel simulation technique to solve the problem (Fattahi and Govindan, 2017).

Daniel and associates (2020) also declared that 8% of the world's current total carbon emissions emanate from logistics and the environment is affected to a great extent. The World Trade Economic Forum (2009) affirmed that 5.5% of the total greenhouse emissions globally originate from logistics. This is inclusive of all types of greenhouse gases not just carbon dioxide. Out of these, two-thirds can be linked to road-transports. Emissions from logistics industry are rising at a greater rate than any other industry and the trend is expected to continue such that by 2030 these levels will be 80 per cent greater than current levels unless there is a change (Daniel et al., 2020). In line with the extant

research, Park et al., (2020) considered the transportation, remanufacturing, and disposal cost. Additionally, Mishra and Singh (2020) minimized the total cost that consisted of remanufacturing, inventory, transportation, import/export, depreciation, and repairing.

In line with the extant research, Tukamuhabwa et al., (2015) asserted that resilience is a firm's adapting ability so it can respond differently depending on the external disturbance; in line with this logic, Pettit et al. believed that resilience a result of a balance between capabilities and vulnerabilities of a supply chain and in order to obtain firm performance, a company should create a balance between them. Excessive vulnerability will cause financial dilemma and over investment on capabilities will deteriorate a firm's profitability. While this point of view can be applied to many cases supply chains, Dabhilkar et al. focused on supply-side resilience, as an adaptive capability that helps the company to handle vulnerabilities (Dabhilkar et al., 2016; Pettit et al., 2010; Ponomarov and Holcomb, 2013; Roghanian & Pazhoheshfar; 2014; Scholten et al., 2019; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015). While Mitroff and Alpasan defined resilience as being proactive and recovering from hardship, Ponomarov and Holcomb showed disapproval with this definition and said resilience is not just about recovery, it is also about flexibility and ability to adapt with negative and positive effects of an environment .(Mitroff and Alpaslan, 2003; Ponomarov and Holcomb, 2013; Solano et al., 2021).

Research methodology

Meta-analytic techniques have become the standard methods for aggregating the results from thematically related studies in the behavioral, health, and economic sciences (Cehovin et al., 2018). In the current empirical survey, a systematic review and meta-analysis were performed to evaluate the model of sustainable reverse logistic strategies and reduction in greenhouse gases as Fig.1.

Fig.1. Flow diagram of search procedure

Conclusion and discussions

The chain and process of producing, reproducing, collecting, handling, disassembling, and transportation are considered as a risky process for environment. Undertaking eco-friendly and cost-effective long-term policies and decision-making can really alter the current circumstance of global warming, reducing emanation of greenhouse gases. Reverse logistics process flow have a prominent role in sustainability of industries by making effort to get the products back, from their final destinations to the suppliers, after use, for remanufacturing, recycling, remanufacturing, or proper eco-friendly disposal. According to the systematic review of the present study, just-in-time green tactics such as resource reduction, socio-economic RL features, moderating final user-function of sensitive materials, can really protect the atmosphere from global warming and reduction in greenhouse gases. Besides, green decision-making factors like dynamic and digitalized infrastructures, web-based endeavors and smart material reuse approaches are discovered in the current investigation. Consequently, this study has declared that long-term green RL targeting and sustainable product and recycle can also improve the companies' competitiveness and customer loyalty (see Fig.2).

Fig.2. the conceptual model of the research (Research findings)

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